

CORRELATION OF FATIGUE BEHAVIOUR IN PRESSURISED HYDROGEN AND ELECTROLYTICALLY SUPPLIED HYDROGEN

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In order to achieve the goal of carbon neutrality in 2050 by the development of a hydrogen-based infrastructure, it is necessary to address the safety and reliability of systems and materials in contact with hydrogen. For this purpose, fatigue tests in high-pressure autoclaves are required, which are limited in number and are very complex in terms of testing. Therefore, another possibility was researched in which the hydrogen was generated by electrolysis on the surface of the material. This study investigated the possibility of adjusting the process parameters of the electrolytic charging in such a way that the specimens of the investigated steel 1.5132 achieve a comparable lifetime in the fatigue tests as in a pressurised hydrogen environment. Following the tests, selected specimens were analysed by thermal desorption analysis to determine the hydrogen uptake. In addition, the fracture surfaces were documented and comparisons made with tests in pressurised hydrogen.

Keywords: Hydrogen, Martensitic steels, Fatigue strength, Life assessment

INTRODUCTION

The European Union is pursuing the goal of becoming climate-neutral by 2050 and massively reducing CO₂ emissions. Analyses have shown that 75 % of the EU's greenhouse gas emissions are due to energy consumption. In order to achieve these goals, it is therefore necessary to reassess the energy system. One pillar of the strategy is the use of clean and renewable fuels, such as green hydrogen and biofuels. Challenges in establishing hydrogen as an energy carrier/storage medium are the production, transport and storage as well as the safety and service life of the systems used. Due to the known influence of hydrogen in contact with metallic materials, the so-called hydrogen embrittlement, it is important to ensure that there are no risks for the safe operation of hydrogen-loaded components and at the same time that efficient system operation with long service lives or running times are possible.

To ensure this, the first step is to carry out material analyses under quasi-static and cyclic loading in order to evaluate the effects of hydrogen on the material properties. This applies not only to plastics for sealing and coating technology, but also to metallic materials in particular. The evaluation of a possible susceptibility to hydrogen can only be derived from material or component tests. Since not many research centres can carry out cyclic fatigue tests under pressurised hydrogen, especially at elevated pressures, it is being investigated whether the hydrogen can also be supplied by other means. Since SSRT-tests have been carried out for many years under electrolytic charging, it was obvious to investigate whether the hydrogen could also be offered electrolytically as part of the cyclic fatigue tests. The results of such analyses are presented below.

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MATERIAL

Tempered and quenched steels, such as 42CrMo4 (Q + T), are essential materials for use in transport components. This material grade has very good strength characteristics and toughness, which is also reflected in its fatigue strength. However, these materials have high CO₂ emissions during production due to the multi-stage and energy-intensive heat treatment consisting of austenitisation, quenching and tempering. For this reason, a new air-hardening ductile forging (AHD) steel has been developed by Stieben et al. [1] and Stieben [2], which, in contrast to precipitation-hardening ferritic-perlitic (PHFP) steels, have a martensitic structure after air cooling. These steels combine the high static and cyclic strengths of quenched and tempered steels with the simple process route of PHFP steels. However, the low impact energy of these alloys has so far prevented their widespread industrial application, but this has been improved in the context of current material (1.5132) developments through the targeted addition of special alloying elements (Gramlich [3], Schmiedl [4], Gramlich [5]). In addition to improving the carbon footprint, the omission of the tempering step has minimised component distortion, reducing the need for component rework, Hagedorn et al. [6].

Martensitic steels under hydrogen exhibit hydrogen embrittlement, which significantly affects their quasi-static properties [7] and reduces fatigue life [8]. In order to use the developed martensitic steel in a hydrogen environment, e.g., for hydrogen engines, extensive qualification testing is required. The tests were carried out on forged U-bolts, which were forged at a forging temperature of 920 – 930 °C and then cooled in air. At the selected forming temperature, a matrix structure is visible in all areas of the spring clip, which is fundamentally different from the previous microstructures. Martensite lancers are only occasionally visible and globular structures in the lower µm range are predominantly visible, Figure 1. If the undeformed and deformed areas are compared, it is noticeable that more areas in the deformed area tend to be lighter in colour. However, the predominantly brown colouring of all samples indicates a complete martensitic transformation.

FIGURE 1 Microstructure of the U-bolts at different positions: forged at 920 °C, AHD steel

Since the length and width of the different lancet packages in martensitic materials are significantly influenced by the former austenite grain size, Pikrin-etchings were carried out for the deformed area to determine this former austenite grain size, Figure 2.

FIGURE 2 Former austenite grain size, forged at 920 °C

Based on the etching, a former austenite grain size of 4.9 μm was determined for the material condition forged at 920 °C without additional heat treatment for both the deformed and undeformed areas. For detailed explanations, including the influence of subsequent heat treatments, please refer ref. [5].

The chemical composition of the investigated material, taken from forged U-bolts, can be found in Table 1 and the quasi-static material properties in Table 2.

TABLE 1 Chemical composition of the investigated material, forged steel 1.5132

	C*	Si	Mn	P	S*	Al	Mo	Ti	Nb	B	N
Target value	0.15	0.50	4.00	min.	min.	0.5	0.2	min.	0.035	0.003	<0,01
Actual value	0.15	0.50	3.90	0.004	0.002	0.52	0.24	<0.001	0.030	0.0025	0.006

* C & S with Leco combustion analysis

TABLE 2 Summary of the determined material characteristics, forged steel 1.5132

Yield strength R _{p0.2} [MPa]	Tensile strength R _m [MPa]	Uniform elongation A _g [%]	Elongation at fracture A ₅ [%]	Notch impact work KV at AT [J]
855	1236	5.2	14.5	47

SPECIMEN GEOMETRIES

Blanks were removed from the shaft area of the forged U-bolts and unnotched round specimens ($K_t \approx 1.0$) were manufactured for material characterisation in air and pressurised hydrogen, Table 3. The surface conditions of the specimens were achieved by machining processes typical for components (fine turning). All specimens examined have a finely turned surface with a roughness $R_z \leq 2.5 \mu\text{m}$, which excludes any influence of surface condition on fatigue strength. Strain-controlled tests were primarily conducted, along with force-controlled tests under axial load. Both specimen geometries shown in Table 3 are identical in the centre retracted area which is critical for failure. The specimens for electrolytic charging have longer clamping areas, which are necessary for proper installation in the media chamber.

TABLE 3 Dimension of the unnotched round specimen, $K_t \approx 1.0$ (all dimensions in mm) and allocation of the specimens to the examinations

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strain controlled tests in air • Strain controlled tests in pressurised hydrogen 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strain controlled tests under electrolytic charging • Force controlled tests under electrolytic charging

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS

Reference tests in air and pressurised hydrogen

A servo-hydraulic test system with a nominal load capacity of 63 kN and equipped with a pressurised autoclave was used for the fatigue tests in air and pressurised hydrogen, Figure 3. In order to assess the reduction in fatigue strength in pressurised hydrogen conditions, strain-controlled fatigue tests were carried out at $R_e = -1$ in air and 50 bar hydrogen atmosphere. The hydrogen used was of quality 5.0 with a purity of 99.999 %. Before the pressurised hydrogen was applied, the autoclave was flushed with nitrogen until an oxygen content of <5 ppm was reached. This purging process and the purity of the pressurised gas ensures that the passive layer formation of the material is inhibited and thus its influence on hydrogen absorption is minimised. The test frequency was 0.1 Hz up to an expected number of cycles of $N_i = 5 \cdot 10^4$ ($\epsilon_{at} \approx 0.3$ %) and for $N_i > 5 \cdot 10^4$ cycles the test frequency was 0.5 Hz to 1 Hz. The waveform was sinusoidal. For the reference tests in air without the influence of hydrogen, the test frequency was also 0.1 Hz up to an expected number of cycles of $N_i = 5 \cdot 10^4$. For an expected lifetime of $N > 2 \cdot 10^5$ cycles, a test frequency of 5 Hz was used. The limit number of cycles for a run-out was set to $N_{lim} = 1 \cdot 10^6$. An extensometer with a gauge length of 10 mm was used to determine the strains in the test area.

FIGURE 3 Experimental setup for the fatigue tests in air and pressurised hydrogen atmosphere

The strain-controlled fatigue tests were evaluated according to the state of the art (Coffin [9], Manson [10], Basquin [11] and Morrow [12]) to derive the strain-life curve and according to Ramberg-Osgood [13] to determine the stress-strain curve.

Investigations under electrolytic hydrogen charging

The fatigue tests under electrolytic hydrogen charging with the longer specimens were also carried out on a servo-hydraulic test system, which was equipped with a special chamber containing a platinum wire and the electrolyte, as shown in Figure 4.

FIGURE 4 Experimentally set-up for electrochemically investigations

The tests under strain control were carried out using a media-resistant extensometer. In addition to the strain-controlled tests, force-controlled tests were carried out for the long-term fatigue regime. The test frequency was set to 0.05 Hz respectively 0.1 Hz. The electrolyte used was 0.1 M NaOH with an addition of 1 g/l thiourea. During the tests, the current density was successively increased, starting at a value of 10 mA/cm², to approach a fatigue life comparable to the tests under pressurised hydrogen. The surface, which was exposed to the electrolyte during the tests, is shown in green in Figure 5. It was determined using CAD and has an area of approximately 830 mm². The clamping areas were not in contact with the electrolyte and therefore not involved in electrolysis and not relevant in the determination of the hydrogen content.

FIGURE 5 Relevant surface for electrolysis and TDA

Determination of the introduced hydrogen content

To determine the introduced hydrogen content in the specimens, thermal desorption analysis (TDA) was carried out with the Bruker G4 Phoenix. In this analysis, a specimen is heated in a defined temperature profile so that the hydrogen effuses from the specimen. The hydrogen is transported to the detector via a carrier gas and quantified. With this method, hydrogen effusion over time can be determined, giving an indication of hydrogen bonding in the material, such as diffusible or trapped hydrogen. After the fatigue tests, the specimens were immediately frozen in liquid nitrogen to prevent hydrogen outgassing. Before the TDA, the specimens were defrosted in an ethanol bath for 5 minutes, weighed and inserted into the device.

RESULTS

Reference tests in air and pressurised hydrogen

Based on the cyclic fatigue tests, the AHD-steel shows a softening material behaviour, Figure 6 and Figure 7.

FIGURE 6 Cyclic stress-lifetime curves for $\epsilon_{a,t} = 0.6\%$ in air and in pressurised hydrogen

Figure 6 shows the cyclic stress-lifetime curves for air and pressurised hydrogen for a total strain amplitude $\epsilon_{a,t} = 0.6\%$. During the first few cycles the material shows a slight hardening. However, a softening can be observed for the majority of the lifetime.

The comparison of the cyclic stress-strain curves in air and pressurised hydrogen is shown in Figure 7. The results do not show any reduction of the endurable strain amplitude in hydrogen atmosphere. The cyclic strain limit $R'_{p0.2}$ in pressurised hydrogen is even higher than in air. This could be a sign that the material has a reduced ductility under pressurised hydrogen. However, this can only be proven beyond doubt by means of tensile tests. However, such experiments have not yet been part of the investigations.

Furthermore, the comparison of the initial load curve in air and the cyclic stress-strain curve in air, Figure 7, confirms the results from Figure 6 in relation to a cyclic softening of the material.

FIGURE 7 Cyclic stress-strain curves and initial load curve in air and pressurised hydrogen

Further evaluations of the influence of the hydrogen environment on the cyclic fatigue behaviour are shown in Figure 8. A significant reduction in fatigue strength is observed when comparing the strain-life curves obtained in air and under pressurised hydrogen. The effect of hydrogen increases as the total strain amplitude increases, resulting in lower fatigue life at the same strain amplitudes and a decrease in the cyclic ductility coefficient ϵ'_f . An total strain amplitude of $\epsilon_{a,t} = 0.8\%$ reduces the lifetime under hydrogen by a factor of around 19 compared to the test results in air. With lower total strain amplitudes of $\epsilon_{a,t} \approx 0.3\%$ and the resulting lower plastic fractions of the total strain, the strain-life curves merge at a number of cycles of around $1 \cdot 10^5$. This shows that the susceptibility of the material to hydrogen increases with a higher fraction of plastic strains in the material during cyclic loading.

FIGURE 8 Strain-life curve in air and pressurised hydrogen, forged steel 1.5132

Comparison of the tests in air and pressurised hydrogen to the tests with electrolytic charging

The aim of the fatigue tests with electrolytic charging was to identify suitable charging parameters to achieve a comparable reduction in lifetime as in pressurised hydrogen atmosphere. Based on the investigations described by Schönborn and Kansy [14], the same electrolyte and current density of 10 mA/cm² were used for the first test in this study. The test frequency was set to 0.1 Hz, comparable to the tests under pressurised hydrogen. As a result of this first test, a lifetime was achieved which was below that of air, but still significantly above that of pressurised hydrogen. To increase the hydrogen uptake, the current density was increased to 20 mA/cm² and 40 mA/cm². However, this did not result in a sufficient reduction in lifetime. All three individual test results achieved a comparable lifetime, which was attributed to the fact that the exposure time was too short and the hydrogen did not have enough time to diffuse into the high stressed areas of the material. The results are shown in Figure 9.

To increase the exposure time, the test frequency was reduced to $f = 0.05$ Hz for further testing. As a result, the number of cycles to crack initiation in the strain controlled tests at $\epsilon_{a,t} = 0.8\%$ and $\epsilon_{a,t} = 0.6\%$ strain amplitude was reduced to a level similar to the results in pressurised hydrogen. Unfortunately it was not possible to further validate these individual test results as the extensometer, which had been custom built for immersion applications, failed due to leakage. To further describe the Woehler curve under electrolytic charging, force-controlled tests were carried out using a stress amplitude equivalent to a strain amplitude of $\epsilon_{a,t} = 0.4\%$ and a test frequency of 0.05 Hz. These tests also achieved a lifetime comparable to that of pressurised hydrogen atmosphere.

FIGURE 9 Strain-life curves in air and under pressurised hydrogen compared to results with electrolytic hydrogen charging

Comparison of the cyclic material behaviour with the introduced hydrogen content

The results of the thermal desorption analyses, which determine the hydrogen content introduced during the tests, are shown in Figure 10. The hydrogen content of the specimens tested in pressurised hydrogen is almost constant, with a value of approximately 0.2 ppm, regardless of the strain amplitude, Figure 10 (left). In contrast, the hydrogen content of the specimens tested with electrolytic hydrogen charging is strongly dependent on the current density and the exposure time respectively the electrical charge Q [C] as a product of the current I [mA] and the time t [s] in the medium. This can be seen very clearly in Figure 10 (right), that the increase of the electrical charge Q leads to higher hydrogen contents. However, scatter in the fatigue life influences this observation.

FIGURE 10 Results of the TDA, hydrogen content as a function of strain amplitude (left) and current density (right)

The correlation between the electrical charge Q and the introduced hydrogen content explains, why the highest hydrogen content was measured for the investigated specimen with a strain amplitude of $\varepsilon_{a,t} = 0.4\%$, which had the longest exposure time. However, it is expected that saturation will occur with sufficient exposure time.

The concentration or distribution of hydrogen in the material structure is significantly influenced by the diffusivity, the local accumulations (in hydrogen traps) and the manufacturing or operating conditions. By analysing the desorption behaviour, important hydrogen transport parameters, especially the trap types, can be revealed. Heating the specimen provides more energy to release hydrogen.

Figure 11 shows the effusion of hydrogen, which is correlated to the detector signal over time for differently charged specimens. In addition, the temperature curve is shown in black. The specimens were heated up to temperature levels of 200 °C, 400 °C and 600 °C. The plotted measurement signal shows that the electrolytic charged specimens contain a large amount of diffusible hydrogen, which effuses at 200 °C. In particular, the red curve for the specimen with the longest exposure time shows very high values. At the highest temperature of 600 °C, the trapped hydrogen also is released. This is an indication that the lifetime is significantly influenced by the trapped hydrogen and not by the diffusible hydrogen.

FIGURE 11 Hydrogen effusion over time during the TDA

Such traps, from which the trapped hydrogen is only released at higher temperatures, are for example solutes, vacancies, dislocations, voids, grain boundaries, phase boundaries and so on. This depends on the desorption energy. According to Kuron [15], the movement and binding energy of the hydrogen in the metal lattice is categorised into: freely movable (8 kJ/mol), shallow traps (<30 kJ/mol) and deep traps (>50 kJ/mol). According to Takai and Watanuki [16], however, only hydrogen from shallow traps has a negative influence on the material properties.

This has not been observed for deep traps. It is also known that martensite has a higher trap density due to finely distributed carbide precipitates, which is responsible for the greater solubility, Dayal and Parvathavarthini [17]. Further evaluations to identify the specific traps have not yet been carried out.

Fractographic analysis of the fracture surfaces

Fractographic examinations of the fracture surfaces of the tested specimens were carried out using a light microscope and a scanning electron microscope (SEM). The results for the specimens tested at a strain amplitude of 0.8 %, which achieved a comparable cyclic fatigue life globally, are shown in Figure 12 and Figure 13. Fatigue testing under electrolytic charging revealed several significant cracks distributed over the entire fracture surface (Figure 12, left side). Electrolytic charging leads to high hydrogen uptake in the surface, resulting in embrittlement of the specimen surface and the formation of multiple cracks. In contrast, the fracture surface of the specimens tested under pressurised hydrogen (Figure 12, right side) exhibits a different morphology, without any side cracks. Gaseous hydrogen continuously penetrates the material at the crack tip, accelerating crack growth.

FIGURE 12 Light microscopic investigation of the fracture surface, left: electrolytic applied hydrogen; right: pressurised hydrogen atmosphere

For further investigation, SEM images of the fracture surfaces were taken (Figure 13). The images above show the edge areas of the fracture surfaces of the specimens at 500x magnification. The electrolytically charged specimen (left side) shows that the cracks are predominantly intercrystalline with only small transcrystalline areas. Specimens tested under pressurised hydrogen (right side) show a higher number of transcrystalline regions. The images below were taken at 5000x magnification. The surface is smooth under electrolytic charging (left side), which indicates low fracture plasticity. Under pressurised hydrogen (right side), honeycomb structures can be seen, indicating ductile material behaviour. This indicates that the influence of pressurised hydrogen is only very localised at the crack tip and promotes crack growth.

FIGURE 13 Examination of the fracture surface with a scanning electron microscope, left: electrolytically applied hydrogen; right: pressurised hydrogen atmosphere

SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

In this paper, investigations on material specimens of the air-hardening ductile forged steel 1.5132 were conducted to show the influence of hydrogen on the cyclic material behaviour. Hydrogen was applied in a 50 bar atmosphere and by electrolytic charging. The following observations were made:

- A significant reduction in fatigue life was observed compared to air, particularly at high strain amplitudes. In the higher fatigue life regime, this harmful influence of the hydrogen was progressively reduced, so that from about 10^5 cycles, a comparable cyclic material behaviour as under air was present.
- The results of lifetime reduction of a pressurised hydrogen environment could be achieved by electrolytically applied hydrogen. However, this required knowledge of the Woehler curve under pressurised hydrogen. Based on this "target size", the parameters of exposure time and current density were optimised in such a way that a comparable fatigue-life behaviour could be achieved.
- The amount of hydrogen introduced during the tests was determined using TDA. Significantly more hydrogen was introduced into the specimen under electrolytic charging than under pressurised hydrogen.

- Through fracture surface analyses, a significant difference in the mechanisms of fracture between the pressurised hydrogen environment and the electrolytically applied hydrogen could be observed. In pressurised hydrogen atmosphere, only a single crack forms, which progresses at a higher rate due to the harmful influence of hydrogen. Under electrolytic charging, a large amount of hydrogen is introduced into the surface of the specimen, causing embrittlement in the edge area, resulting in the formation of a large number of cracks.

To clarify the remaining questions, further studies are planned. In addition to further fatigue tests to validate the Woehler curve, permeation measurements and diffusion measurements under pressurised hydrogen and electrochemistry are also planned in order to be able to better describe the hydrogen input.

In summary, it must be noted at this point that it is currently not possible to replace a pressurised hydrogen environment that exists in reality with electrolytic boundary conditions.

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